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**SOVEREIGNTY AND THE MISERY
OF
SMALL EASTERN EUROPEAN NATIONS**

Hent Kalmo

IMAGINE Working Paper No. 42

Abstract: It has been said that countries in East-Central Europe have their own brand of constitutionalism which celebrates the idea of national sovereignty. I shall argue that, when the question of sovereignty is treated in the framework of cultural imaginaries, we realise that this region's constitutionalism is actually much less archaic than it might seem. Despite all the diversity encountered in East-Central Europe, there is a recurring cultural theme running through it: the idea of being a small nation that has suffered great historical tragedies. Yet no political or legal position with respect to sovereignty follows from the mere observation that the nation is small and in need of protection. As the history of East-Central Europe shows, depending on the kind of threats that are thought to besiege the nation, state sovereignty may appear either as a protective shield or an obstacle precluding membership in some larger political community. Even supposing that countries in East-Central Europe share a collective mentality centred on the category of the nation, it does not follow that they should be especially attached to state sovereignty in any traditional sense.

KEYWORDS: Sovereignty; East-Central Europe; Nationalism

Author is a Research Fellow at the Johan Skytte Institute of Political Studies at the University of Tartu.

Email: hent-raul.kalmo@ut.ee

IMAGINE has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 803163). More information can be found at <https://www.imagine-const.eu/>.

Sovereignty and the Misery of Small Eastern European Nations

Hent Kalmo

One of the idiosyncrasies of the countries in Eastern and Central Europe is supposed to be their especially strong attachment to sovereignty. Ivan Krastev has argued that Europe's East-West divide is also inscribed in political imaginaries, and that this fact was clearly visible at the time of the EU's Eastern enlargement. In contrast to the anti-nationalist postmodern vision that had emerged in the West, 'the Eastern European nation-states that joined the EU in 2004 were rather obsessed with the ideas of national sovereignty and ethnic homogeneity', claims Krastev.¹ Or, as Rogers Brubaker has put it: at the time when Western Europe seemed to be moving *beyond* the nation-state, Eastern Europe was apparently moving *back* to it.² Of course, even in Western Europe, it has never been obvious to everyone that the nation-state is on the way out. The ideas of sovereignty and the nation-state have often been questioned in a polemical mode, vis-à-vis those who believe that, whatever the innovations in the legal architecture of the EU, these novelties do not call for a fundamental revision of constitutional categories. Others have insisted that the nature of the EU could never be captured without the imagination being expanded beyond the already familiar. As Joseph Weiler memorably said in reference to the Maastricht decision of the *Bundesverfassungsgericht*, to describe the EU without rethinking in creative ways the concept of a polity was to be 'looking backwards, like Lot's wife', to something based on the tired old idea of an ethno-culturally homogenous people.³ Against the background of such discussions of the new and the old in constitutional thinking, East-Central Europe has tended to appear as a site of almost comic archaism. According to Anneli Albi, when the recently restored countries of East-Central Europe began to consider EU membership, they did so from the perspective of a traditional idea of sovereignty, centred on such ideas as independence, ethnically defined nation-state and

¹ Ivan Krastev, Re-imagining the East-West divide in Europe (IWMpost 129: European boundaries and divides) <https://www.iwm.at/publication/iwmpost-article/reimagining-the-east-west-divide-in-europe> accessed 15 March 2024.

² Rogers Brubaker, 'Nationalizing states revisited: projects and processes of nationalization in post-Soviet states' [2011] 34 *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 1785-6.

³ J. H. H. Weiler, 'Does Europe Need a Constitution? Demos, Telos and the German Maastricht Decision' [1995] 1 *European Law Journal* 223.

national self-determination.⁴ In a similar vein, Signe Larsen has contended that post-communist countries have retained their own brand of constitutionalism which celebrates ‘the ideas of nationalism, the nation-state and national sovereignty.’⁵

When faced with such claims, and reflecting on the role of constitutional imaginaries, the first question that comes to mind is whether it could make sense to ascribe a uniform constitutional ideology to a region as large and variegated as East-Central Europe. But if constitutionalism is not an ideology or a worldview, weaving together a set of consistent beliefs about the nation, the state and sovereignty, then what could be meant by saying that these concepts are nonetheless central to the constitutionalism of East-Central Europe? Needless to say, sovereignty itself can be imagined in various ways. There is even a long tradition of portraying sovereignty as a myth – something with no corresponding reality other than the force by which it captures the imagination.⁶ Hans Kelsen decried the ‘dogma of sovereignty’ and accused it of inhibiting the development of international law.⁷ Resistance to European integration has sometimes also been explained by the strength of outdated ideas.⁸ Indeed, to suppose that some national judiciaries remain in thrall to a conception of sovereignty as an absolute and indivisible power, would this not make it hard for them to see it as shared or parcelled out in a way that European integration is assumed to require? And if this is true, are not countries in East-Central Europe particularly exposed to sovereigntism by their shared constitutional outlook? On the other hand, if their proneness to distinct ways of thinking about the nation and its relation to the state – assuming that such regional idiosyncrasies exist – do not translate directly into any legal doctrines, or even an attachment to some traditional notion of sovereignty, then how could their views about the nation be depicted as *constitutional* ideas or imaginaries, as opposed to more general social representations that might be populating the mind of those interpreting the law?

⁴ Anneli Albi, *EU Enlargement and the Constitutions of Central and Eastern Europe* (CUP, 2005) 122; see also Anneli Albi, ‘Postmodern Versus Retrospective Sovereignty? Two Different Discourses in the EU and the Candidate Countries?’ in Neil Walker (ed), *Sovereignty in Transition* (Hart Publishing, 2003) 401.

⁵ Signe Rehling Larsen, ‘Varieties of Constitutionalism in the European Union’ [2021] 84 *Modern Law Review* 496.

⁶ See, for example, Francis Delaisi, *Political Myths and Economic Realities* (Viking, 1927); Walter G. O’Donnell, ‘The Myth of Sovereignty’ [1949] 24 *Social Science* 91.

⁷ Hans Kelsen, *Das Problem der Souveränität und die Theorie des Völkerrechts. Beitrag zu einer reinen Rechtslehre* (Verlag von J. C. B. Mohr, 1928) 236.

⁸ Jacques Ziller, ‘Sovereignty in France: Getting Rid of the Mal de Bodin’ in Neil Walker (ed), *Sovereignty in Transition* (Hart Publishing, 2003) 261.

Despite all the diversity encountered in East-Central Europe, there is, in fact, a recurring cultural theme running through this region: the idea of being a small nation that has suffered great historical tragedies. This theme certainly gives rise to an imaginary of sorts, a very rich imaginary even, which loses its subtlety when reduced to such catch-all expressions as ‘ethnic nationalism’. A distinction should be made between the general concept of the nation and the particular set of ideas that a group of people entertain about themselves as a nation, such as the idea of being a small afflicted nation situated in a dangerous area.⁹ The latter is an example of the kind of social myth that offers an identity to a collective and thereby becomes an essential part of collective imaginaries.¹⁰ Attempts have already been made to find some common themes in the political myths of East-Central Europe (for example, the theme of a civilizational bulwark against the East), and to distinguish their varieties in different countries (aside from such particular national myths as the Holy Crown of Hungary or Polish messianic martyrdom).¹¹ If the idea of being a long-suffering small nation is to be considered a common regional myth of this sort, then it, too, must be understood in a sufficiently vague manner, allowing for variation in what exactly the predicament of the nation consists in and what historical tragedies it has suffered. Moreover, if this idea is to be taken as a constitutional imaginary, that is, something bringing diffused cultural representations of nationhood into the legal domain, then not after the mode of a definite worldview. No political or legal position with respect to sovereignty follows from the mere observation that the nation is small, endangered, and therefore in need of protection.

Contrary to what has been suggested by Benedict Anderson – who famously defined nations as imagined communities – the nation is not always imagined as a sovereign entity, destined to inhabit a sovereign state.¹² The national imaginary may be more open-ended. Depending

⁹ This crucial distinction has been underlined, for example, by Max Scheler in ‘Der allgemeine Begriff von „Nation“ und die konkreten Nationalideen’ in *Schriften zur Soziologie und Weltanschauungslehre* (Franke Verlag, 1963) 334.

¹⁰ On social myths as key elements of collective imaginaries, see Gérard Bouchard, *Social Myths and Collective Imaginaries* (University of Toronto Press, 2017) 4.

¹¹ Walter Kolarz, *Myths and Realities in Eastern Europe* (Kennikat Press, 1946) 72. On the Holy Crown of Hungary as a myth, see László Péter, ‘The Holy Crown of Hungary, Visible and Invisible’ [2003] 81 *The Slavonic and East European Review*. On Polish messianism: Geneviève Zubrzycki, ‘Polish mythology and the traps of messianic martyrology’ in Gérard Bouchard (ed), *National myths. Constructed pasts, contested presents* (Routledge, 2013) 110.

¹² Anderson wrote that the nation is ‘imagined as sovereign because the concept was born in an age in which Enlightenment and Revolution were destroying the legitimacy of the divinely-ordained, hierarchical dynastic realm. Coming to maturity at a stage of human history when even the most devout adherents of any universal religion were inescapably confronted with the living *pluralism* of such religions, and the allomorphism between each faith’s ontological claims and territorial stretch, nations dream of being free, and, if under God, directly so.’

on the kind of threats that are thought to besiege the nation, state sovereignty may appear either as an all-important protective shield or, on the contrary, an obstacle precluding membership in some larger political community where the nation could fare better than in solitude. In other words, even supposing that countries in East-Central Europe share a collective mentality centred on the category of the nation, and that this mentality induces them to pose fundamental political problems through a particular lens, it does not follow that they should be especially attached to state sovereignty in any traditional sense. Rather than viewing constitutionalism as an expression of some definite ideology, it might be more helpfully approached from the perspective of the problems that are deemed essential by those who practice it. On this reading, constitutionalism is a language that simultaneously frames and engenders disagreements about issues related to constitutional interpretation. As will be shown below, the ‘nationalist rhetoric of the small nation’, as Siniša Malešević has described it, is also an axis of debate which functions by continuing to stir up new, often contradictory ideas that can be built into rivalling constitutional doctrines.¹³ When the question of sovereignty is treated in this framework, we will see that East-Central Europe’s constitutionalism is actually much less archaic than it might seem. Not merely is it open to revising the concept of national sovereignty. It positively invites questions that point beyond tired old ideas about nation-statehood.

The misery thesis

It is remarkable how consistently descriptions of East-Central Europe have advanced some version of what might be called the misery thesis. All nuances aside, the thesis is broadly about an Eastern *Sonderweg*: the idea that the region is different from Western Europe now because its history has been different. In other words, the thesis has two parts. It asserts, on the one hand, that the region possesses some distinguishing characteristics (a particular

The gage and emblem of this freedom is the sovereign state.” Benedict Anderson, *Imagined Communities. Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism* (Verso, 2006) 7.

¹³ Jan Komárek has argued similarly that the central concepts forming part of any constitutional imaginary are ‘contested truths’ around which important political arguments turn. Jan Komárek, ‘European Constitutional Imaginaries. Utopias, Ideologies, and the Other’ in Jan Komárek (ed), *European Constitutional Imaginaries. Between Ideology and Utopia* (OUP 2023) 2-3. On ‘small nation’ as a rhetorical category, see Siniša Malešević, *Grounded Nationalisms. A Sociological Analysis* (CUP 2019) 126.

political culture, a type of nationalism different from the one current in the West) and, on the other, that this peculiarity is best explained by going back to the past, in some cases to the Middle Ages or beyond. This line of thinking finds its *locus classicus* in the famous essay ‘The Miseries of East European Small States’ by István Bibó, a Hungarian political theorist who wrote at the time of the Second World War, attempting to make sense of the catastrophe that he had seen unfolding by laying bear its deep origins. Contrary to the view that was dominant in Hungary, Poland and Czechoslovakia, – the three states he was mostly concerned with, alongside Germany which he also assigned to Eastern Europe –, Bibó argued that the neighbourhood’s small states had not appeared in pre-war dramas merely in the role of victims but had made a large contribution to international tensions with their chronically maladjusted, at times grossly anti-democratic internal politics. For him, the fundamental question for understanding the catastrophe was this: Why had the region abandoned democracy and political liberalism after hailing them so enthusiastically in the wake of the First World War? Bibó’s explanation was that, whilst the cause of freedom and the cause of nationalism had progressed harmoniously in the West, these ideals had drifted apart in the East. A sequence of traumatic collective experiences had led to the conviction that democracy cannot be realised without jeopardising the national community. Not only leaders but the populations of small Eastern European states had come to believe that, if they cared about the fate of their nation, they simply could not afford to implement democracy and political freedoms to the full, however much they may have approved of these values in the abstract.

Bibó’s thesis was not only about the predicament resulting from someone imagining (wrongly, he emphasised) that there is an incompatibility between democracy and national welfare or even survival. For understanding how this mistaken conclusion could be drawn, and how it could ensconce itself in the mind of Eastern Europeans as a putative lesson of history – prompting them to develop ‘the greatest monstrosity of modern European political development: anti-democratic nationalism’¹⁴ – one had to revisit the process by which nations had first emerged in this region. Bibó claimed that the great divergence between East and West could be traced back to the circumstances of nation-building in various parts of Europe. In the West, nations took shape and had the opportunity to mature within pre-existing states, with the result that national and state boundaries overlapped when masses

¹⁴ István Bibó, ‘The Miseries of East European Small States’ in István Bibó, *The Art of Peacemaking. Political Essays by István Bibó* (Yale University Press, 2015) 151 (emphasis omitted).

began to be drawn to nationalism at the time of the French Revolution. The Eastern lands, by contrast, were under the power of great empires in the 19th century, so that the smaller nations inhabiting this space, unable to realise their aspiration to statehood, were reduced, *faute de mieux*, to cultivating their language and folk customs – not as a pastime but to prove that nations were more real, more solid entities than the existing states. According to Bibó, it was not smallness as such which produced the impasse from which Eastern national movements hoped to escape by a turn to a *völkisch* identity. Small nations also existed in the West, but they fared much better, noted Bibó, pointing to Belgians, Danes and others as examples. The main distinguishing factor in the East was the presence of loosely integrated, semi-fixed political organisations: not sufficiently implanted to create national loyalties corresponding to state boundaries (to swallow up the small nations, as it were), yet strong enough to prevent fragmentation and consolidation along national lines (the formation of small nation states). Such conditions prevailed only in Central-Eastern Europe and for this reason, as Bibó put it, linguistic nationalism became the region's specialty.

Bibó was not the first to emphasise the lack of overlap between national and state borders in Eastern Europe and to remark on the importance of this fact for the mentality of the region's inhabitants. In 1915, at the time of the First World War, Tomáš G. Masaryk had told a London audience that if they wanted to understand Eastern Europe they needed not a political but an ethnographic map. 'An Englishman, speaking of his nation, identifies the nation and state. Not so the Serb or the Bohemian, because to his experience state and nation do not coincide, his nation being spread over several states, or sharing a state with other nations.'¹⁵ Not that this was a great misfortune, from Masaryk's point of view. Although he spoke of Eastern Europe as an ethnological 'danger zone' ridden with cultural and political conflict, for him, there was no misery in the condition of its small nations. Yes, they were latecomers in staking their claim to statehood, but their prospects were bright. Small nations were no less able to protect themselves if sufficiently determined to resist attacks. Masaryk conceded that the nations of East-Central Europe might suffer from some disadvantages, such as a more limited population and a weaker economy, but these handicaps were the result of imperial

¹⁵ Tomáš G. Masaryk, 'The Problem of Small Nations in the European Crisis' in R. W. Seton-Watson, *Masaryk in England* (CUP 1943) 142.

oppression. 'Let the smaller nations be free: do not interfere, leave them alone, and these drawbacks will soon disappear.'¹⁶

Here was an authoritative view of Eastern Europe that underlined the small size of its nations yet was thoroughly optimistic in tenor. How did the misery thesis emerge then? It started to take shape at the time when the 'danger zone' of small nationalities became a scene of many independent states. In the mid-1920s, Edvard Beneš, the foreign minister of Czechoslovakia could still confidently maintain that most of these states were committed to freedom and democracy. Beneš admitted that the region was beset with the problem of discontented ethnic minorities, but he brushed this difficulty aside and, like Masaryk, depicted current difficulties as a legacy of imperial misrule ('a bad training for the present majorities and minorities alike').¹⁷ What brought about a crucial change in perspective (reflected in Bibó's later analysis) was the claim that the most fateful legacy of the imperial period was a distortion in how Eastern Europe nations imagined themselves. Outside observers pointed out a discrepancy between the self-understanding of the new countries as 'national states' and the fact that none of these states included only one single nation.¹⁸ Bibó took up this line of reasoning, contending that, when small Eastern European nations gained statehood, they were still captivated by the territorial fantasies they had developed under imperial domination, and acting as if these aspirations were somehow more real than the reality. As Walter Kolarz put it in his study of the myths of Eastern Europe (1946), beside every actually existing state, there was a 'shadow State shaped by the nationalist imagination'.¹⁹ To see the potential clashes between these various shadow states, one only needed to draw a graph of the divergent claims. 'The result would be a multitude of intersecting circles in which every intersection would denote a conflict, not between the nations themselves, but between their historical theories of the State. Poles and Czechs can find the way to an understanding; but the notions of the "Bohemian State Rights" or the "Historic Poland" could never be brought into one formula. There is no reason why Slovaks, Rumanians and Hungarians should not dwell side by side in amity, but the conceptions of a "Greater Moravian Empire", of a "St. Stephen's Empire" and of a "Dako-Rumanian Empire" can never be reconciled. The same is true of Greater Albania and Greater Greece, Greater Bulgaria and Greater Serbia, Greater

¹⁶ Ibid, 148.

¹⁷ Edvard Beneš, 'The Problem of the Small Nations after the World War' [1925] 4 *The Slavonic Review* 272.

¹⁸ C. A. Macartney, *National States and National Minorities* (OUP 1934) 210.

¹⁹ Walter Kolarz, *Myths and Realities in Eastern Europe* (Kennikat Press, 1946) 74.

Lithuania and the Polish *Rzecz Pospolita* (Commonwealth). The whole picture of Central and Eastern Europe presents an inextricable skein of conflicting national claims.’²⁰

Even today, the canonical picture of Eastern Europe’s misery is that of a strange nationalist fantasy world saturated with historical memories. The ‘demons of the past’ appear to be especially active in this region.²¹ The main thrust of such arguments is that East-Central Europe’s idiosyncrasies cannot be explained by the simple fact that the region remained on the wrong side of the Iron Curtain. ‘If one regards Soviet Communism as a disease, then it seems that Eastern Europe may have had a pre-disposition to the infection’, wrote one historian.²² In the mid-1990s, Tony Judt tried to show that the line dividing Eastern from Western Europe is not an artificial creation dating from the Cold War, – ‘recently drawn across a single cultural space’ – but rather something older and more real. Similarly to Bibó, Judt made much of the fact that Eastern European peoples were confronted with a well-formed state system at the time they came to political consciousness. ‘To have been formed into a recognized nation and a permanent state in earlier centuries was to have been extraordinarily fortunate’, wrote Judt. ‘Whereas the northern and western European peoples formed states by expansion from a core, absorbing their own peripheries until constrained by topography or competition, the countries of modern eastern Europe were born and could only be born from the collapse of empires – Russian, Turkish, Austrian, German – a process that is still incomplete... This is *the* great misfortune of the eastern half of Europe: that its division into states came late and all at once. It is what gives to these lands their common history and their common weakness – and it is what in the end makes them crucially different from the luckier peoples to the west.’²³

Admittedly, it is not quite obvious why the circumstances of the birth of Eastern European states should be essential for understanding their character today. Why should developments in the 19th century and earlier be relevant to an enquiry into the region’s present political

²⁰ Walter Kolarz, *Myths and Realities in Eastern Europe* (Kennikat Press, 1946) 74.

²¹ See e.g. R. Krakowsky. *Le populisme en Europe centrale et orientale. Un avertissement pour le monde?* Fayard, 2019, 244. For example, the prospect of immigration is said to reawaken the painful memory of living as a minority in an empire and the difficulties of dealing with other nationalities in an independent state during the interwar period. S. Kauffmann. *Europe’s Illiberal Democracies*. – The New York Times, March 9, 2016; R. Krakowsky. *Le populisme en Europe centrale et orientale. Un avertissement pour le monde?* Fayard, 2019, 244.

²² Philip Longworth, *The Making of Eastern Europe* (Palgrave Macmillan, 1992) 7.

²³ Tony Judt, *A Grand Illusion? An essay on Europe* (Penguin Books, 1996) 56. Judt also argued that the collective identity of the region’s peoples was formed around the experience of making ‘an all-or-nothing claim to territory and power at the expense of a neighbour making an identical claim – in many cases over the same land.’ *Ibid.*

culture? Bibó offered an answer that was to prove extraordinarily influential: the region has supposedly acquired a traumatised identity as a result of its history.²⁴ The theoretical paradigm in which Bibó worked was that of collective psychology.²⁵ Within this paradigm, it was natural to think that, if past collective experiences have been negative, then the present can literally suffer from history, in the form of a neurosis, for example, or a national inferiority complex that leads to a sense of impotence and a desire of compensation.²⁶ Bibó described how major shocks (such as revolutions, foreign invasions, military defeats) can make communities behave as if they were hysterical individuals: lose touch with reality, be constantly afraid of conspiracies, display both insecurity and overblown self-assessment. Unable to come to terms with an overwhelming trauma, a community concocts various make-believe solutions in an effort to ensure by all means that the catastrophe will not be repeated. ‘These are the situations when a nation behaves as though it were unified while it is not, as though it were independent while it is not, as though it were democratic while it is not, and as though it were involved in revolution while it is only languishing.’²⁷ Bibó claimed that, although some Western European countries have also suffered from a ‘collective hysteria’, Eastern Europe is especially susceptible to this condition because of its unique calamity-filled history.

A somewhat similar relationship between history and collective mentality was presented in another text that became a *locus classicus* on regional misery. Milan Kundera’s ‘The Tragedy of Central Europe’ (1984) also described the weight of history and its lasting effect on the mind of those who may not have experienced personally any great traumas. Indeed, Kundera asserted that an element of trauma is part of the very idea of a small nation. ‘But what is a small nation?’, he asked, after having highlighted the importance of this notion for understanding the identity of Central Europe (an ‘uncertain zone of small nations between

²⁴ One author has also spoken of a ‘wounded identity’; A. Máté-Tóth, *Freiheit und Populismus. Verwundete Identitäten in Ostmitteleuropa* (Springer, 2019) 101.

²⁵ Maurice Halbwachs, one of the most prominent representatives of this field, described it as being concerned with ‘a collective mentality [that] exists and that is not like a lost, isolated and negligible province, but exerts an influence upon all the functions of individual mentality which cannot be understood or explained without it.’ Maurice Halbwachs, ‘Individual Psychology and Collective Psychology’ [1938] 3 *American Sociological Review* 616.

²⁶ Oliver Brachfeld, *Inferiority Feelings in the Individual and the Group* (Grune & Stratton, 1951). For a study that seeks to trace the slow historical formation of a national inferiority complex in a particular context, see Paul Johansen, ‘Nationale Vorurteile und Minderwertigkeitsgefühle als soziale Faktor im mittelalterlichen Livland’ in Alexander Bergengruen and Ludwig Deike (eds), *Alteuropa und die moderne Gesellschaft. Festschrift für Otto Brunner* (Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1963) 88.

²⁷ István Bibó, ‘On the Balance of Power and Peace in Europe’ in István Bibó, *The Art of Peacemaking. Political Essays by István Bibó* (Yale University Press, 2015) 46-7.

Russia and Germany’).²⁸ He offered his famous definition: ‘the small nation is one whose very existence may be put in question at any moment; a small nation can disappear, and it knows it.’ Kundera claimed that, for the inhabitants of Central Europe, this awful knowledge is not merely an abstract truth but a harrowing lesson of history. ‘A Frenchman, a Russian, or an Englishman is not used to asking questions about the very survival of his nation. His anthems speak only of grandeur and eternity. The Polish anthem, however, starts with the verse: “Poland has not yet perished...”’. This statement – ‘Our nation has not yet perished’ – captures, according to Kundera, Central Europe’s particular vision of the world. The crucial difference from Bibó is that Kundera did not depict this attitude as pathological in any way. When ‘the devastating march of History’ produces a vision based on distrust and existential fear, the outcome is hard-won wisdom, not a hysteria, Kundera suggested. By contrast to Bibó, who was continually insisting on the distorted character of the imaginaries born out of catastrophes, opposing the fantasies of a traumatised nation to a healthy society’s true picture of its surroundings, Kundera seems to have thought that contemporary history (notably, the eastward expansion of Russia) was confirming the lessons that Central Europeans had drawn from their past.

Although Kundera was thus uninterested in the phenomenon of nationalist self-deception, – which Bibó considered central to Eastern Europe’s misery – the emphasis on perception in his definition of smallness is very illuminating for understanding the functioning of imaginaries. If smallness is seen as a collective mentality rather than an objective, numerically quantifiable fact, then it matters little if some nation is actually small, or indeed whether there is such a thing as a nation at all outside the cognition of individuals. What matters is that the category of being a small nation is being used to make sense of the world. Moreover, as already mentioned, Kundera situated smallness geographically, speaking of a zone between two large neighbours, Germany and Russia. For the purpose of studying imaginaries, it, again, matters little if *we* designate the relevant area as Central or Eastern Europe, or whether the region defined by reference to national fragility exists at all in some objective sense. The important consideration is that smallness and location are unified into an essential nexus – national vulnerability is perceived geopolitically, against the background of some geographical place that is seen as determining for the nation’s prospects. National

²⁸ Milan Kundera, ‘The Tragedy of Central Europe’ in Milan Kundera, *A Kidnapped West. The Tragedy of Central Europe* (Faber & Faber, 2023) 31.

identity nearly always includes an idea of a homeland.²⁹ This must be true in the case of a ‘small nation’ as defined by Kundera, for existential danger is hard to imagine separately from a ‘politico-geographic situation’, to use the expression by which Friedrich Ratzel sought to capture all the consequences of belonging to a particular place (climate, borders, size, relations with neighbouring states).³⁰

The ‘misery of small Eastern European nations’ can thus be understood in two very different ways. It can refer to an objective condition of vulnerability or, alternatively, it can denote a collective self-image that foregrounds vulnerability. Consequently, the misery thesis may also be reinterpreted as a claim about the potency of a certain kind of rhetoric in East-Central Europe. This is how Miroslav Hroch has approached the problem of ‘small nations’ in his influential account of nation-formation under foreign domination. According to this account, it is via stereotypes, such as the tendency to represent the nation as a person with its own history, that the experience of living in a multi-ethnic empire has been preserved and continues to impact the present.³¹ The leaders of dominated national movements idealised smallness, but they also reacted defensively against claims that their nation was a fiction. ‘This gave rise to the ensuing feeling of permanent endangerment of the nation – which was later transformed into a lasting stereotype – as well as an urge to prove the legitimacy of one’s own national existence.’³² Analysing post-communist countries, Hroch argued that the imperial background of East-Central European history resulted in some ‘permanent characteristics’ that are still present in the collective mentality of its inhabitants. ‘Identification with a national group includes, as it did in the last century, the construct of the personified and personalised nation’, wrote Hroch in 1992. ‘The glorious history of this personified nation is understood as the, or a, personal past of each of its members. Its defeats are understood as personal failures and continue to affect their feelings.’³³

²⁹ See Jan Penrose, ‘Nations, states and homelands: territory and territoriality in nationalist thought’ [2002] 8 *Nations and Nationalism* 277. On the relationship between geography and national identity, see David Hooson (ed), *Geography and National Identity* (Blackwell, 1994).

³⁰ Friedrich Ratzel, ‘Über die geographische Lage. Eine politisch-geographische Betrachtung.’ in Hans Helmolt (ed), *Kleine Schriften von Friedrich Ratzel*, Volume 2 (R. Oldenbourg, 1906) 257.

³¹ Miroslav Hroch, ‘Nationalism and national movements: comparing the past and present of Central and Eastern Europe’ in Miroslav Hroch, *Comparative Studies in Modern European History. Nation, Nationalism, Social Change* (Routledge, 2007) 38.

³² Miroslav Hroch, ‘An unwelcome national identity, or what to do about ‘nationalism’ in the post-communist countries?’ in Miroslav Hroch, *Comparative Studies in Modern European History. Nation, Nationalism, Social Change* (Routledge, 2007) 271.

³³ *Ibid*, 270.

We do not have to suppose that all countries in East-Central Europe are equally suitable for an analysis emphasising smallness and fragility even at the level of perception. As we saw, one version of the misery thesis regarding Eastern Europe is that its national myths are loaded with dangerous megalomania. But a great nation with a heroic past can suddenly become small and vulnerable when the mode of interpretation is switched from glorious to tragic, yielding a retrospective impression that its whole history has been overshadowed by the ‘fear of the slow death of a small nation’, as Paul Lendvai has said regarding Hungarians.³⁴ By unifying the past and present, and thereby grounding social identity, the category of the nation exhibits the typical structure of a myth, understood not as a false story but as a narrative employed for particular social purposes.³⁵ “When the object of history is the nation,” remarked Ladislav Holy in his overview of Czech self-stereotypes, “it is its imagined existence over time which makes possible the construction of the enduring ‘we’ who imagine ‘our history’ and unproblematically utter, as Czechs do, the phrase ‘We have suffered for three hundred years.’”³⁶ Since myths support social identities, the two may be seen as interchangeable, yet there is clearly no such thing as a single, universally shared national identity, nor should we look for *the* national myth with respect to any collective. Identity politics can take the form of a debate over whether the nation is small or not.³⁷ However, even when this happens, the category of smallness is still imposed as a frame of political thought.

The idea of post-traumatic sovereignty

One important characteristic of a myth is that, rather than something fixed, it is a theme which allows for the emergence of many variants or elaborations as the ‘work on myth’

³⁴ Paul Lendvai, *The Hungarians. A Thousand Years of Victory in Defeat* (Princeton University Press, 2003) 1.

³⁵ For a conception of myth as an origin story which is not inherently opposed to history, see William H. McNeill, *Mythistory and Other Essays* (The University of Chicago Press, 1986) 3.

³⁶ Ladislav Holy, *The little Czech and the great Czech nation. National identity and the post-communist transformation of society*, CUP, 1996, 117.

³⁷ Christian Axboe Nielsen, ‘Whoever says that Serbia is small is lying!’. Serbia, ontological (in)security and the unbearable smallness of being’ in Samuël Kruizinga (ed), *The Politics of Smallness in Modern Europe. Size, Identity and International Relations since 1800* (Bloomsbury Academic 2022) 133.

progresses.³⁸ In this way, the idea of being a small endangered nation can be continually updated, added new subthemes or varieties of existential threat – such as demographic decline, for example – so that it becomes a political myth that never ceases to resonate with the times.³⁹ But how exactly should we think about the political implications of such myths? Does the imaginary of being a small nation entail any definite views on sovereignty? The thesis that there exists a strong connection between the two, – that perceived national misery of the kind observable in Eastern Europe leads to an obsession with sovereignty – has been defended perhaps most comprehensively by Jarosław Kuisz who has introduced the idea of ‘post-traumatic sovereignty’ to express precisely this nexus. Kuisz starts from Kundera’s observation that it can be an essential, identity-forming experience for the inhabitants of some country that their state may be wiped away. Once this possibility is recognised, and seared on the mind, as it were, the reappearance of foreign domination becomes the preeminent, all-embracing fear. For Kuisz, the paradigmatic case of such a traumatised condition is Poland where, as he says, the state’s survival is the primary consideration in approaching nearly all fundamental political problems (with repeated references being made to the 18th-century partitions and other similar calamities, like the *annus terribilis* of 1939, when the country was again carved up by Nazi Germany and Soviet Union). Kuisz claims that even the dispute over the rule of law that started in 2015 ‘should be understood and interpreted against the background of the trauma of the disappearance of the Polish state from the map of Europe’.⁴⁰ Whilst the connection may not be evident at first sight, it is precisely the idea of sovereignty that provides the link: the effect of past catastrophes has been to engender an obsessive determination never to lose political independence again, so that everything resembling it will henceforth be perceived as anathema. ‘The loss-of-sovereignty argument is constantly in play,’ writes Kuisz, ‘although it is sometimes rhetorically re-packaged to better suit the twenty-first-century context.’⁴¹

³⁸ On the idea that myth is a process that develops by continuous work on a theme, see Hans Blumenberg, *Work in Myth* (The MIT Press, 1985).

³⁹ Attempts have been made to distinguish between myths in general and specifically political myths, relying either on their content or on the close relation that some shares narratives have to political conditions and actions; see Henry Tudor, *Political Myth* (Macmillan 1972) 138, Chiara Bottici, *A Philosophy of Political Myth* (CUP 2007) 180. It might be less controversial to speak simply of the politics of myth, without classifying myths into political and non-political, as does Bruce Lincoln in *Discourse and the Construction of Society. Comparative Studies of Myth, Ritual, and Classification* (OUP 1989) 27.

⁴⁰ Jarosław Kuisz, *The new politics of Poland. A case of post-traumatic sovereignty* (Manchester University Press 2023) 197.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

Kuisz mostly dwells on Poland and its national imaginaries of doom, but he argues that East-Central Europe as a whole is suffering from a traumatised attitude to sovereignty, since the inhabitants of most, if not all, countries in this region have supposedly internalised the condition that Kundera thought is defining for a small nation.⁴² Loss-of-sovereignty arguments are also frequently heard elsewhere, of course. But Kuisz maintains that they have particular undertones in East-Central Europe where they are ‘fuelled by all sorts of regionally and nationally specific backgrounds from the past.’⁴³ On the face of it, this claim appears as the latest iteration of a particular kind of misery theme about the political ideology of Eastern Europe. It has been an influential view that history has endowed, or infected, this region with a special variety of nationalism centred on ethnicity. Whilst Western civic nationalism is taken to be relatively benign and nice, the Eastern ethnic variety is seen as ‘doomed to nastiness by the conditions which gave rise to it.’⁴⁴ Another widely-held belief is that ‘ethnic nationalism’ is not merely an outlook about nationhood but also, implicitly at least, a political worldview characterised by a veritable obsession with sovereignty. Carlton Hayes, an important early figure in the study of nationalism, wrote that it is ‘a basic part of the nationalist creed, in which every citizen of a national state is now educated, that absolute sovereignty is a right inherent in his national state and that any impairment or threatened impairment of such sovereignty is a wrong which cries to Heaven – and to himself – for vengeance.’⁴⁵ Although Hayes was not talking about any specific form of nationalism, others have argued that, when adherents of ‘ethnic nationalism’ attain statehood, they, especially, will exalt sovereignty as a high, if not the highest value. In other words, it is thought that ‘ethnic nationalism’ does not morph into something essentially different when the aim of statehood is achieved. On the contrary, it is the state that is rendered cultural and ethnic in orientation, the leaders of the former national movement now having the ambition to enable the core nation to fully permeate the political organisation that has been created. Rogers

⁴² Ibid, 201. Similarly to Kundera, Kuisz also attributes the main role to Russia when uncovering the sources of post-traumatic sovereignty, seeing his interpretation validated in the widely diverging reactions in Eastern and Western Europe to Russia’s all-out aggression against Ukraine in 2022. Ibid, 188.

⁴³ Ibid, 203.

⁴⁴ This is how Ernst Gellner has described the views of John Plamenatz on ‘Eastern nationalism’; see Ernst Gellner, *Nations and Nationalism* (Cornell University Press, 1983) 99; John Plamenatz, ‘Two types of Nationalism’ in Eugene Kamenka (ed), *Nationalism. The Nature and Evolution of an Idea* (Edward Arnold, 1976) 34.

⁴⁵ Carlton J. H. Hayes, *Essays on Nationalism* (Russell & Russell, 1966) 167.

Brubaker has argued that all states in Central-Eastern Europe are and will be nationalising (and not civic) in this sense, at least to some degree.⁴⁶

Now, if our interest is in constitutional imaginaries, and the alleged divide between East and West, how could we possibly test the theory that, in East-Central Europe, statehood is imagined according to what Brubaker calls a ‘nationalist understanding of the world’ which views the political universe as being made up of ‘sovereign, independent and culturally distinctive nation-states.’⁴⁷ We can certainly assemble a lot of material that seems to show that states in this region have valued sovereignty. For example, the historian Vojtech Mastny has attempted to demonstrate that East-Central Europe has historically exhibited an aversion to federalism. ‘Federal structures of any kind had been exceptional and federal thinking at best marginal in the part of Europe whose modern history had been so prominently shaped by an ethnic quest for self-assertion within national states’, writes Mastny.⁴⁸ He recalls the words of Edvard Beneš who said that federalism reminded the region’s inhabitants of their past as subject nationalities under imperial domination. Some additional evidence for reluctance to parting with sovereignty could perhaps be derived from the 1950s when a group of exiled politicians and diplomats from nine East-Central European countries (Albania, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland and Romania) drew up a joint report assessing the prospect of eventually joining the federal projects that were being launched in Western Europe at the time. The group noted that, even though the countries under Soviet rule realised the need for European integration, they were so attached to their national characteristics and cultural independence that they could only countenance pooling some limited sovereign rights.⁴⁹ Many other such examples could be found. To come to the more recent period, is it not the case that some East-Central European countries have

⁴⁶ Rogers Brubaker, *Nationalism reframed. Nationhood and the national question in the New Europe* (CUP, 1996) 104. Trying to establish a contrast between Western and Eastern Europe, Alfred Cobban, another influential historian, wrote in a similar vein in the 1940s: ‘Once the ideal identification of cultural nation and political state has become accepted, the state in its own defence tends to act as if it were a single and united nation from the cultural point of view, and if in fact it is not this, it must endeavour to make the facts correspond to the ideal, regardless of the rights and liberties of those among its citizens who do not belong to the majority nation.’ Alfred Cobban, *The nation state and national self-determination* (Crowell, 1970) 110. Brubaker has later somewhat qualified his views, see Rogers Brubaker, ‘Nationalizing states revisited: projects and processes of nationalization in post-Soviet state’ [2011] 34 *Ethnic and Racial Studies*.

⁴⁷ Rogers Brubaker, ‘Populism and nationalism’ [2020] 26 *Nations and Nationalism* 8.

⁴⁸ Vojtech Mastny, ‘The Historical Experience of Federalism in East Central Europe’ [1999] 14 *East European Politics and Societies* 94.

⁴⁹ *Europe. Nine panel studies by experts from Central and Eastern Europe. An examination of the Post Liberation Problem of the Position of Central and Eastern European Nations in a free European Community* (Free Europe Committee, Inc, 1954) 3.

been contesting with unmissable vehemence the legitimacy of the EU in the name of sovereignty, sometimes going as far as declaring its core treaties unconstitutional?⁵⁰

The first objection that suggests itself is that sovereigntism is hardly specific to East-Central Europe.⁵¹ The more fundamental problem, however, is that the relationship between ‘ethnic nationalism’ and sovereignty is, in fact, deeply ambiguous. Theories which associate some sort of general worldview with ‘ethnic nationalism’ tend to obscure the concrete aspects in the representation of the nation (whether it is seen as small or large, for example), assuming, mistakenly, that such nuances are immaterial in comparison to what is considered typical, namely, that the outlook is ethnic rather than civic. Also, if the nation precedes the state in the imagination of its adherents, in line with the typical scenario envisaged by the category of ‘ethnic nationalism’, then it means that the nation is separable from the state and can be thought independently of the legal concept of sovereignty traditionally associated with statehood. For understanding how nations and their political destinies were imagined against the background of empires as they existed in East-Central Europe in the 19th century, we can evoke the famous letter that the Czech scholar František Palacký sent to the Frankfurt Parliament in 1848. Palacký said that the Czech nation had a vital interest in the continued existence of a strong multi-national Austrian state because it needed protection from the menacing expansion of Russian power to its east. The disappearance of smaller nations in the Austrian Empire was not a danger, Palacký argued, so long as its constitution was built on the right principles.⁵² In the ensuing decades, there was indeed a growing strand of thinking which presented sovereign statehood as a natural goal for every truly respectable nation – a sign that a nation had reached full personhood.⁵³ National fragility was sometimes adduced

⁵⁰ Nathalie Brack, Ramona Coman, Amandine Crespy, ‘Sovereignty conflicts in the European Union’ [2019] *Les Cahiers du Cevipol* 22; Lisa H. Anders, Astrid Lorenz, ‘Examining Illiberal Trends and Anti-EU Politics in East Central Europe from a Domestic Perspective: State of Research and Outline of the Book’ in Astrid Lorenz, Lisa H. Anders (eds), *Illiberal Trends and Anti-EU Politics in East Central Europe* (Palgrave 2021) 2.

⁵¹ For different forms of sovereigntism in Western Europe, see Thomas Guénolé, *Le souverainisme* (Humensis, 2022) 59.

⁵² ‘If the bond which unites a number of diverse nations in a single political entity is to be firm and enduring, no nation can have cause to fear that the union will cost it any of the things which it holds most dear. On the contrary, each must have the certain hope that in the central authority it will find defense and protection against possible violations by neighbours of the principles of equality. Then will every nation do its best to confer upon that central authority such powers as will enable it successfully to provide the aforesaid protection.’ František Palacký, ‘Letter to Frankfurt, 11 April 1848’ in Balázs Trencsényi and Michal Kopeček (eds), *Discourses of Collective Identity in Central and Southeast Europe (1770–1945), Vol 2, National Romanticism. The Formation of National Movements* (Central European University Press, 2007) 327.

⁵³ Johann Caspar Bluntschli, *Allgemeines Staatsrecht* (J. G. Cotta, 1863) 88.

as a consideration for acquiring independent statehood as a form of protection.⁵⁴ Yet by no means was this a self-evident position for someone who asked, liked Masaryk, at the end of the 19th century: ‘how can a small nation survive and remain independent?’⁵⁵ If political structures were assessed by their ability to further the intellectual and material flourishing of the nation, then it could be argued that a strong empire is, in fact, preferable to a small nation-state. Given the geopolitical realities at the turn of the 20th century (as the leaders of national movements saw them), the smallness of the nation could also be a strong argument *against* seeking an independent state.

The notion that all small East-Central European states whose political culture was dominated by the idea of an ethnically or culturally defined nation were obsessed with sovereignty as a result of their having emerged from empires is historically quite inaccurate. Of course, once political independence is achieved, it will tend to become a cherished ideal. The imaginary about nationhood is enriched, becoming multi-layered as it now encompasses ideas about one’s own state and, in addition, some conception of how the state and the nation cohere. A process of mixing, compounding and rearrangement quickly starts. Citizens of the new state are likely to be too attached to the idea of their nation enjoying sovereignty for wishing to revert back to older ‘ethnic’ ideas of merely cultural independence. History will to be re-written in a way that depicts the state as the crowning achievement of the nation, misrepresenting the past as an inevitable liberation from imperial domination, as if political sovereignty has always been the goal.⁵⁶ In reality, as David J. Smith and John Hiden have written about developments in the Habsburg and Russian empires, nation-statehood was mostly thrust upon subject peoples ‘as a result of the sudden collapse of the dynasties under the pressures of war and revolution.’⁵⁷ Natasha Wheatley has similarly argued that, if the inauguration of the successor states is narrated ‘purely within the tracks of nationalist history – as the self-actualization of freestanding national units – we risk obscuring the extent to

⁵⁴ Notably by Roman Dmowski who argued in 1903 that the fragmented Polish nation could perish if it is not brought together again in a restored Polish state; Roman Dmowski, ‘Gedanken eines modernen Polen (Myśli nowoczesnego Polaka)’ in Martin Faber (ed), *Roman Dmowski: Schriften* (Brill, 2023) 138.

⁵⁵ Tomáš G. Masaryk, ‘The Czech Question’ in Ahmet Ersoy, Maciej Górny and Vangelis Kechriotis (eds), *Discourses of Collective Identity in Central and Southeast Europe (1770–1945), Vol 3/1, Modernism – The Creation of Nation-States* (Central European University Press, 2007) 205.

⁵⁶ The assumption that cultural nations always want to become states has been recently contested in André Liebich, *Cultural Nationhood and Political Statehood. The Birth of Self-Determination* (Routledge, 2022).

⁵⁷ David J. Smith, John Hiden, *Ethnic Diversity and the Nation State. National cultural autonomy revisited* (Routledge, 2012) 9. For a similar argument, see Aviel Roshwald, *Ethnic Nationalism and the Fall of Empires. Central Europe, Russia and the Middle East 1914–1923* (Routledge, 2001) 2.

which their modes of self-presentation and self-understanding might originate not with the “nation” but with the empire they ostensibly shucked off.’⁵⁸

Wheatley claims that the states created after the First World War transported a whole imperial-constitutional imaginary from their imperial origins into the new world order. ‘Far from a juridical tabula rasa in Central Europe, the Paris system moved into a landscape already populated with the ghosts of imperial orders past.’⁵⁹ There was also continuity in thinking about the nation, however, for ideas about imperial constitutionalism were built into national imaginaries, as the case of Palacký shows. The fundamental dilemma of a ‘small nation’ endured. ‘What good is political independence if the nation is not economically independent?’, Masaryk had asked in 1905. ‘Some Balkan states are independent in name only. In reality decisions about them are made by neighbouring states or only by some large banks.’⁶⁰ As we saw, ten years later, when the First World War had broken out, Masaryk was extremely sanguine about the prospects of small Eastern European nations, albeit without denying that they had some economic drawbacks. By this time, he had come to embrace the idea of an independent Czech nation-state.⁶¹ Yet this hardly means that the considerations he mentioned earlier – the advantages of a greater economic space, the fact small states are dominated by great powers – suddenly became irrelevant. These very same considerations had made the idea of creating a federation attractive in the Balkans.⁶² When new states were erected on the ruins of empires in East-Central Europe, they could also be considered as being independent in name only. Formal sovereignty was not a guarantee of independence.⁶³ In the mid-1930s, when the League of Nations had proven ineffective, Northern and Eastern European small states adopted neutrality as their official line of policy, agreeing to the watering down of the League’s Covenant, preferring greater independence, freedom of action and the absence of any security commitments.⁶⁴ This did not result from any abstract

⁵⁸ Natasha Wheatley, *The Life and Death of States. Central Europe and the Transformation of Modern Sovereignty* (Princeton University Press, 2023) 189.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Tomáš Garrigue Masaryk, *Kroměříž Lectures. Problem of a Small Nation* (Nakladatelství TRIGON, 2010) 31.

⁶¹ Considering his earlier statements, it is doubtful whether this had happened by 1905 as claimed in Roman Szporluk, *The Political Thought of Thomas G. Masaryk* (Columbia University Press, 1981) 124.

⁶² See Janko Sakasoff, ‘Neoslawismus, Balkanföderalismus und Sozialdemokratie’, [1911] 4 *Der Kampf* 212.

⁶³ ‘Gaining the status of a sovereign state might place a country on the same formal footing as all its peers’, the historian Aviel Roshwald has written in reference to the interwar period in East-Central Europe. ‘But outside the world of military parades, diplomatic balls, and state dinners lurked the reality of a Hobbesian international system in which big states ate little states for breakfast and then spat out the bones.’ Aviel Roshwald, ‘The Post-1989 Era as Heyday of the Nation-State?’ [2011] 24 *International Journal of Politics, Culture, and Society* 12.

⁶⁴ Zara Steiner, *The Triumph of the Dark. European International History 1933-1939* (OUP, 1933) 359.

conception of sovereignty, however. Neutrality was felt to be the only viable option once it had become clear that all dreams of collective security and federal union had failed.

Before the Second World War, most governments were reluctant to take on the kind of commitments that multiplied later (the protection of individual rights, the creation of supranational bodies, etc). No Pan-European federation emerged, despite the fact that international and constitutional lawyers began to hail the voluntary limitation of sovereignty as a sign of enlightened thinking.⁶⁵ The size of the catastrophe that befell East-Central Europe in the late-1930s, which made any status quo solution impossible there, explains why its politicians were among the first to imagine a new political order not merely for their region but for Europe as a whole. ‘After this war, Europe must become an entity, political and economic’, said Władysław Sikorski, the Prime Minister of Poland, calling for a new approach to cooperation in 1941. ‘The State, for example, must begin by relinquishing some of its sovereign rights, if this is necessary in order to reach agreement with a neighbouring State on matters of common interest, especially when the basic problem of security and defence is concerned.’⁶⁶ At this time, Sikorski was negotiating a federal agreement with the Czechoslovak government whose representative Edvard Beneš, in spite of his earlier remarks on federalism’s lack of appeal to a post-imperial mentality, also claimed that only by creating a larger bloc can small nations improve their economic conditions and strengthen collective security.⁶⁷ As was noted by commentators, the humiliating fate of Central European countries had caused political thinkers to revise their views on state sovereignty. ‘After the last war [i.e. the First World War] even the smallest nations aspired to complete independence, but they found it only led to isolation in the face of danger [...] Today the idea of closer international associations is coming to the fore, so that nations may combine to resist aggression by their stronger neighbours.’⁶⁸

The conclusion to be drawn is not that past traumas have made East-Central European countries more, rather than less, willing to curb their sovereignty. Decades of ‘limited

⁶⁵ Hent Kalmo, ‘Sovereignty and European Exceptionalism’ in Anne van Aaken, Pierre d’Argent, Lauri Mälksoo and Johann Justus Vasel (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Law in Europe* (OUP 2024).

⁶⁶ ‘The Post-War World’ [1942] 12 *Current Notes on International Affairs* 214.

⁶⁷ Edvard Beneš, ‘Hitler’s New Order and the New European and World Order’ (Lecture at Cambridge University, May 1941) cited in: *Czechoslovakia in Post-War Europe. Problems of Reconstruction* (The New Europe Publishing Co., 1942) 11. For these negotiations, see Piotr S. Wandycz, *Czechoslovak-Polish Confederation and the Great Powers, 1940-43* (Greenwood Press 1978) 38.

⁶⁸ “*Wiadomości Polskie: ‘A Central European Confederation’*” [1942] in Walter Lipgens (ed), *Documents on the History of European Integration, Volume 1: Continental Plans for European Union 1939-1945* (Walter de Gruyter 1985) 636.

sovereignty' under Soviet rule certainly established untrammelled independence as a desirable goal. Soviet domination was often compared to colonialism, so that the language of self-determination became a natural idiom for the 'captive nations' of East-Central Europe.⁶⁹ Nonetheless, as Jarosław Kuisz is keen to stress, the condition of post-traumatic sovereignty does not posit agreement on where the greatest threat to political independence lies after the shocks that have caused this neurotic state. It only stipulates that the threat of losing sovereignty is now the fundamental, never-forgotten consideration in approaching political issues. The inevitability of disagreements can be brought home by considering another 'post-' condition: the inability of a once-imperial nation to come to grips with its diminished status. In attempts to explain Brexit, references were made to British political culture and history, some arguing that the wish to 'take back control' is 'deeply embedded within the political psyche of a large group of British citizens'.⁷⁰ But interpretations of Britain's imperial past shaped arguments both for and against membership in the EU. The EU could be presented in two contrasting ways, either as an obstacle to or a vehicle for Britain's imperial ambitions. As has been said, this ambiguity 'requires us to recognise post-imperial patterns of thought, not as a psychological affliction to which only half the population is subject, but as a common cultural inheritance through which all sides think and argue.'⁷¹ In the case of Britain, we may thus speak of post-imperial sovereignty, not having in mind any doctrine but something crucial about British political culture, namely, that the question of sovereignty is there embedded in particular patterns of thought. These patterns do not yield any consistent set of political views, nor even a belief in the value of sovereignty as traditionally understood. Britain's attitude to European integration has been aptly described as 'Euro-equivocation'.⁷²

⁶⁹ On the emergence of the expression 'captive nations', see Anna Mazurkiewicz, *Voice of the Silenced Peoples in the Global Cold War. The Assembly of Captive European Nations, 1954–1972* (De Gruyter, Oldenbourg, 2021). On the comparison of Soviet rule with colonialism as experienced in Africa and Asia, see James Mark, Bogdan C. Iacob, Tobias Rupprecht, Ljubica Spaskovska (eds), 1989. *A Global History of Eastern Europe* (CUP, 2019) 174.

⁷⁰ Anand Menon, Alan Wagner, 'Taking back control: sovereignty as strategy in Brexit politics' [2020] 8 *Territory, Politics, Governance* 279.

⁷¹ Robert Saunders, 'Brexiteer and Empire: 'Global Britain' and the Myth of Imperial Nostalgia' [2020] 48 *The Journal of Imperial and Commonwealth History* 3. Another explanation offered for Brexit was geography and how it has configured Britain's relationship with Europe over a very long period. The historian Ian Morris claimed that, only when facts are put 'into this framework do we see why Brexit seems so compelling to some, so appalling to others'; Ian Morris, *Geography is Destiny. Britain and the World, a 10 000-Year History* (Profile Books, 2022). Whatever one might think of this explanation specifically, or of the relationship between Brexit and geography, the observation is again that geography explains both the Leave and the Remain vote by suggesting completely different implications to different groups.

⁷² Brian Harrison, *Finding a Role? The United Kingdom 1970-1990* (OUP, 2010) 20.

If we distinguish between general patterns of thought, or political languages, on the one hand, and particular arguments formulated within these languages, on the other, then the idea of post-traumatic sovereignty would pertain to the level shared by various political camps existing within a country. This means that it cannot be understood as a worldview with a set of clear-cut beliefs about what endangers sovereignty and how to best protect it. Such beliefs pertain to the level where disagreements appear about the central problem, namely, how to ensure that political independence is not lost. On this reading, it becomes much less problematic to portray the idea of post-traumatic sovereignty as a regional phenomenon. Countries in East-Central Europe cannot be lumped together meaningfully for all purposes. What Kuisz claims is that, despite all the differences between their individual historical experiences, countries in this region are similar in being small nations in the sense used by Kundera – they share a sense of existential danger derived from these experiences. This does not condition these countries to adopt any single position on the value of retaining unlimited independence as opposed to joining some larger organisation. The imaginary of misery can accommodate a whole variety of positions, depending on how the predicament attributed to the nation is articulated in political and legal terms. Even if we assume attachment to national independence as a vague general goal, it leaves open a series of hard problems. What exactly is independence? Is it captured by the legal concept of sovereignty? Can it be hollowed out in a federal organisation? Consensus cannot be expected on such questions, especially since they express ambiguities in the very idea of sovereignty. When threats are seen to emanate from various sources, not merely from legal limitations on decision making, then the same political position (for example, joining a federation) can be seen as either compromising or protecting sovereignty. In the presence of such difficulties, it is indeed equivocation we should expect, not consistency and agreement.

Post-communism and the ‘sovereignty conundrum’

In the light of what has been said above, we can also form a better understanding of an apparent inconsistency in the behaviour of post-Soviet countries or what Wojciech Sadurski has called the ‘sovereignty conundrum’, referring to an irony he noted in the eastern enlargement of the EU. ‘Countries with a proud national history,’ Sadurski wrote in 2004,

‘which have only just emerged from several decades of humiliating and oppressive domination by the Soviet Union (at worst being subjected to forceful integration into Soviet statehood as in the case of the Baltic states), and at best suffering all the burdens and disadvantages of ‘limited sovereignty’, are now about to embark upon the surrender of the sovereignty again, this time for an admittedly benign foreign body, but a foreign body nevertheless.’⁷³ Indeed, how can this be explained? How to account for the wish of post-communist countries to join the EU when, as several authors have claimed, theirs was a strongly sovereigntist outlook, either because East-Central Europe had missed the aggiornamento of constitutional imagination that the West had experienced since the 1950s or because the Soviet era itself had produced a form of constitutionalism that favours an archaic conception of nation-statehood? According to Signe Rehling Larsen, one important effect of the Soviet period was to ingrain the idea that threats to democracy emanate primarily from foreign oppressors (from ‘them’, not ‘us’). Hence, she says, the image of a pure, ethnically defined nation, deserving of unlimited freedom, and the ‘constitutional emphasis on nationalism and sovereignty’.⁷⁴ But if so, there really is a puzzle. If the mindset of the post-Soviet countries was ‘incompatible with the constitutional reality of the Union they were acceding to’, as Rehling maintains⁷⁵, how could these countries not merely join the EU but subscribe to even deeper forms of integration later?

Different explanations have been offered for the ‘sovereignty conundrum’. According to Anneli Albi, it was in virtue of some strange naiveté that lawyers in East-Central Europe failed to make their idea of national sovereignty a serious obstacle to the process of accession to the EU. ‘Although constitutional awareness about the EU gained ground as accession drew closer, Central and Eastern European scholars tended to devote minimal space to analysing the nature of the EU polity, and to view the Union therefore merely as an international organisation or a confederation of states, finding that it would not significantly affect national sovereignty.’⁷⁶ Sadurski has detected more strategy in the efforts of constitutional scholars to create theories which define the problem away by showing that accession to the EU actually involves no loss of sovereignty. Their role has been, in his view, either to back up with constitutional arguments political choices made for other reasons or to influence decisions by

⁷³ Wojciech Sadurski, ‘The Role of the EU Charter of Rights in the Process of Enlargement’ in Georg A Bermann and Katharina Pistor (eds), *Law and Governance in an Enlarged European Union* (Hart 2004) 71.

⁷⁴ Signe Rehling Larsen, ‘Varieties of Constitutionalism in the European Union’ [2021] 84 *Modern Law Review* 497.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

⁷⁶ Anneli Albi, *EU Enlargement and the Constitutions of Central and Eastern Europe* (CUP, 2005) 123-4.

helping to convince the political class and the society at large that their old-fashioned ideas regarding sovereignty and the nation are not at all incompatible with European integration. Thus, some commentators have downplayed the unique character of the EU, emphasising that all international treaties entail a surrender of sovereign rights, – this being itself an exercise of sovereignty – and that the difference is simply one of degree. It is also said that some important powers are retained by Member States or that the transfer is not irrevocable. ‘In conclusion,’ writes Sadurski, ‘legal constitutional scholarship in the accession states is working hard to reconcile the state-focused discourse of sovereignty with the legal realities of the EU accession, and in so doing it constructs a legal fiction whereby the transfer of some, even crucial, powers to the supranational level does not amount to a transfer of sovereignty, but only to a transfer of the exercise of some sovereign powers.’⁷⁷

One difficulty with such explanations is that they assume what the fact of the matter is with regard to the EU, namely, that it involves a loss of sovereignty, so that there appears to be an element of deception or at least artificiality in the work of constitutional layers who deny this. In reality, sovereignty is a contested idea and the multiplicity of its meanings can produce genuine disagreements about its continuing relevance even in an organisation as deeply integrated as the EU.⁷⁸ From the point of view of constitutional imaginaries, the more important point is this, however: such explanations also assume too much about what can be deduced from the kind of lofty rhetoric that is encountered in constitutional texts. There is little doubt that some of the constitutions in East-Central Europe celebrate sovereignty in exalted terms. For example, the preamble to the Polish constitution (1997) reads: ‘Homeland, which recovered, in 1989, the possibility of a sovereign and democratic determination of its fate...’ This line conveys a sentiment that can certainly be described as pride and joy in the possession of sovereignty. The late-1980s witnessed an explosion of such rhetoric in East-Central Europe. To illustrate the solemnity that was common at the time, we can recall a speech that Bronislavas Genzelis, a Lithuanian politician gave in 1989: ‘Until a nation does not regain independence, its existence is constantly endangered. If a nation has necessary conditions to develop its culture, it is alive; if it has its own economy, it exists, but without political independence it only vegetates.’⁷⁹ When the Lithuanian Constitution was adopted a

⁷⁷ Sadurski, ‘The Role of the EU Charter of Rights in the Process of Enlargement’, 79.

⁷⁸ See especially Michel Troper, ‘The survival of sovereignty’ in Hent Kalmo and Quentin Skinner (eds), *Sovereignty in Fragments. The Past, Present and Future of a Contested Concept* (CUP, 2011) 132.

⁷⁹ Bronislavas Genzelis, ‘Nation and Sovereignty’ in Bronislavas Genzelis, *The restitution of Lithuania’s statehood* (Lithuanian National Museum 2007) 108.

few years later, its opening words struck a similar note. As if to dispel any prospect that the nation will have to vegetate again in constant danger, Article 3 provided: ‘No one may limit or restrict the sovereignty of the People or make claims to the sovereign powers of the People.’⁸⁰

Whilst it would be hard to claim that such statements do not demonstrate an attachment to political independence, they nonetheless tell us very little about how sovereignty is actually understood in the constitutional culture that informs the interpretation of these texts. The ‘sovereignty conundrum’ may cease to need an explanation, once we discover that there has been no objective inconsistency in joining the EU under the cover of independence-minded rhetoric. Let us suppose that the Soviet shock indeed produced, or reinforced, a condition of post-traumatic sovereignty – that is, an obsession with political independence – in post-communist countries. However, as noted by Jarosław Kuisz, one of the expressions of this condition is a Europeanist position which is quite willing to accept the limitations that membership in the EU brings. These limitations are accepted not because of some theoretical notion of sovereignty or a lack of understanding about the incompatibility of these limitations with a traditional idea of sovereignty. The rationale is that membership in the EU strengthens political independence. From this point of view, there is no conundrum, since it is precisely the experience of foreign domination that is thought to weigh in favour of EU membership. Perhaps too schematically, Kuisz divides Poland into two political camps, sovereigntists and Europeanists, attributing to each a reasonably consistent set of views about how Polish sovereignty should be defended. Both camps are supposedly traumatised by Poland’s past. Both are fully committed to the imperative of not allowing Poland’s political independence to be taken away again. And unsurprisingly, both believe that their views, not those of the other camp, reflect the correct interpretation of Polish history. Sovereigntists look back to interwar Poland, often idealising it, extracting from it what they see as relevant, and project this vision into the future as a model of maximal sovereignty. ‘The opponents of the Polish sovereigntists interpret the events of the traumatic past differently. For the Europeanists, membership of the EU is what guarantees the permanence of the state in a content and form adequate to the twenty-first century. They accuse their opponents of an anachronistic understanding of the state, inadequate for a globalised world. Europeanists are ready for novelty, including the experiment of building European structures. They invariably regard

⁸⁰ See Anneli Albi, *EU Enlargement and the Constitutions of Central and Eastern Europe* (CUP, 2005) 26.

Russia as the main threat to Polish sovereignty and consider power plays within the EU to be the lesser evil, far better than unrestricted competition of the former nation-states in pre-1939 Europe.’⁸¹

To generalise beyond Poland, rather than ascribing a single constitutional ideology or outlook to a country, it might be more appropriate to distinguish between several competing outlooks, without denying thereby the existence of a common framework of ideas and representations.⁸² The presence of some overarching framework and a multiplicity of views within this structure are both central elements if we wish to recognise the indisputable fact of fundamental disagreements and still retain the notion that these disagreements are embedded in a shared collective inheritance. In Poland, the Law and Justice party has directed its loss-of-sovereignty rhetoric mostly against the EU. This party possesses a ‘worldview’, as Wojciech Sadurski calls it, which it shares with Hungary’s Fidesz and which it hopes to make dominant in all of East-Central Europe – a vision that ‘is primarily based on a suspicion of the outside world, and on the celebration of national sovereignty as the supreme value in a nation’s policy, which needs to be forever defended and strengthened.’⁸³ Kuisz describes the ideology of the Law and Justice party in nearly identical terms, but he adds a crucially important caveat: its liberal opponents are similarly attached to national sovereignty, only *they* warn against Poland leaving the EU and thereby finding itself exposed to Russian aggression.⁸⁴ Although sovereigntists and Europeanists agree on the importance of preserving sovereignty, they disagree on whether some kind of fundamental equivalence can be established between the threats emanating from Russia and the EU. Those opposing the Law and Justice party are not blind to the imperfections of the EU. Nor are they necessarily unable to appreciate the difficulty of reconciling the present configuration of the EU with a traditional notion of sovereignty. What they believe, according to Kuisz, is that these problems are either secondary or merely apparent when compared to the much more serious danger posed to Polish sovereignty by Russia.⁸⁵

⁸¹ Jarosław Kuisz, *The new politics of Poland. A case of post-traumatic sovereignty* (Manchester University Press 2023) 203.

⁸² For an attempt to describe different political cultures in France, see Serge Bergstein (ed), *Les cultures politiques en France* (Éditions du Seuil, 1999).

⁸³ Wojciech Sadurski, *Poland’s Constitutional Breakdown* (OUP, 2019) 12.

⁸⁴ Jarosław Kuisz, *The new politics of Poland. A case of post-traumatic sovereignty* (Manchester University Press 2023) 197.

⁸⁵ *Ibid*, 202.

So, returning to the question of misery, the collective self-image of being a small endangered nation can be considered as precisely the kind of overarching structure of meaning which operates by framing an on-going debate, rather than dictating any political positions or legal doctrines. For clarifying the nature of constitutional imaginaries and their role in legal reasoning, it might be useful to start from Carl Schmitt's famous classification of different types of legal thinking, in particular, the distinction between normativism and concrete-order thinking. Schmitt claims that there exist some socially consecrated images (or 'concrete-order notions', as he calls them) such as brave soldiers, duty-conscious bureaucrats, respectable comrades, and so on, which a strictly normativist understanding ('rule and statute thinking') excludes from the law altogether since it considers that they have no direct legal relevance. Actually, says Schmitt, such concrete notions are central to law as abstract rules never enforce themselves but are applied by people in well-determined situations, against the background of concrete patterns of social order which should be honoured, not ignored, according to Schmitt.⁸⁶ Irrespective of whether one agrees with this last point (on the need to respect established social institutions), Schmitt's analysis can be taken as an insightful portrayal of how constitutional reasoning really proceeds. It directs our attention to the strange outskirts of law inhabited by ghostlike figures 'which normatively cannot exist'.⁸⁷ The idea of concrete-order thinking calls to mind the observation by Clifford Geertz that some of the most critical decisions concerning the direction of public life are not made in formal institutions such as parliaments but in the unformalized realms of the collective consciousness, at the level of the 'conceptual structures individuals use to construe experience'.⁸⁸

Whatever their deep cultural sources, it is undeniable, however, that decisions are also made in parliaments and courts. This begs the question of how exactly do the collective images that swirl in a culture enter the realm of formal decisions. Summing up the literature on why national courts have accepted the jurisprudence of the CJEU, Karen Alter has distinguished between two rival approaches: legalism, which invokes only legal logic and reasoning to explain national court behaviour, and neo-realism, which puts the emphasis on politics and the pursuit of national interest. Alter criticises both approaches, legalism mainly for ignoring politics and neo-realism for not offering any clear account of how the 'national interest' is

⁸⁶ Carl Schmitt, *On the Three Types of Juristic Thought* (Praeger 2004) 54-5.

⁸⁷ *Ibid*, 55.

⁸⁸ Clifford Geertz, *Interpretation of Cultures. Selected Essays* (Basic Books, 1973) 314.

constituted.⁸⁹ One way to bring in culture into this analysis would be to assert that politicians and judges are indeed seeking to further the national interest, only that they understand it in a pre-conditioned manner, in the light of a concrete, culturally informed view of what is the situation of the ‘nation’. It has long been recognised that the national interest which influences decisions is not something objective but a reflection of the images that deciders form of their environment.⁹⁰ But even this line of analysis would yield an excessively simplified picture of judicial reasoning. Legal arguments are mostly not a mere dressing up, devised *ex post* after having latched on some idea of the national interest. One suspects that few constitutional scholars would accept the claim that, in assessing whether membership of the EU involves a loss of sovereignty, all they are doing is making some pre-determined decision about the national interest palatable to an audience. On the other hand, it would be equally unconvincing to say that, when engaging in this kind of exercise, their eyes are fixed on some abstract notion of sovereignty which they merely unpack by the rules of logic.

What other frame of mind could there be, then, if legal arguments must retain some force yet also be penetrated by a sense of the concrete situation? Although this might not be how Schmitt himself viewed it, concrete-order thinking could be seen as being directed by what Hans-Georg Gadamer has described as a ‘fore-conception’.⁹¹ Interpretation always starts from some provisional understanding, replaced by a more suitable one if the expectations of the interpreter are not met. Like Europeanists and sovereigntists in general, scholars and judges may also be impelled by an impression of where the greatest danger lies given the concrete situation of their nation, without this fore-conception necessarily determining their conclusions about the law. They could have a Europeanist sensibility and believe that military aggression is what really threatens their small nation, – much more than any formal limitations within the EU – yet still be swayed by some arguments in favour seeing sovereignty (as enshrined in the constitution) as an obstacle to European integration. Some legal arguments may appear simply irresistible to them. What their fore-conception brings to the reasoning is an articulation of the situation in terms of concrete facts and circumstances – conceptual structures individuals use to construe experience, to recall the definition of culture offered by Clifford Geertz. The ‘sovereignty conundrum’ grows out of the assumption that

⁸⁹ Karen Alter, ‘Explaining National Court Acceptance of European Court Jurisprudence: A Critical Evaluation of Theories of Legal Integration’ in Anna-Marie Slaughter, Alec Stone Sweet and J. H. H. Weiler (eds), *The European Court and National Courts – Doctrine and Jurisprudence. Legal Change and Social Context* (Hart 1998).

⁹⁰ Joseph Frankel, *National Interest* (Palgrave Macmillan 1970) 110.

⁹¹ Hans-Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method* (Continuum 2006) 269-270.

there is no fundamental difference between the Soviet Union or the EU at the level of the idea of foreignness. As Sadurski noted, for all its benign character, the EU is also a foreign body. However, concrete-order thinking does not start from such abstract notions as a 'foreign body'. The fact that one body appears benign and another dangerous for the nation is of fundamental importance from its point of view.